

VAT4MAV: Visual Active Tracking for Micro Aerial Vehicles

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Abstract—Visual active tracking has become an increasingly prominent topic in robotics because of its central role in applications such as assistive robotics and surveillance. Unlike passive tracking, active methods tightly couple perception and control: the system not only detects the target but also actively maneuvers the platform to keep it in view. While much of the literature focuses on ground robots, solutions for aerial platforms remain scarce. To address these issues, in this extended abstract we present our ongoing work on visual active tracking for micro aerial vehicles, focusing on the comparative evaluation of two complementary design strategies. The first adopts a modular approach, in which perception and control components are developed separately and then integrated into a pipeline; the second follows an End-to-End approach, where a single deep policy directly maps visual observations to control commands through reinforcement learning. By contrasting these paradigms, our goal is to assess their relative strengths, limitations, and applicability to real-world deployment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro Aerial Vehicles (MAVs) have attracted increasing interest due to their agility, light weight, and low cost, which make them well-suited for a wide range of robotic applications. These operational scenarios demand fast, reliable perception and control loops to guarantee task success.

In this work we focus on the Visual Active Tracking (VAT) problem, where a tracker vehicle must keep a moving target visible and centered within the camera field-of-view (FoV). Active tracking tightly couples perception and control so that the platform actively maneuvers to maintain the target within the FoV. This makes VAT substantially more challenging, since it requires a direct mapping from high-dimensional visual observations to real-time control actions.

Classical vision-based control has been mainly addressed through position-based visual servoing (PBVS) and image-based visual servoing (IBVS) [1]. In PBVS, image features are processed to extract the 3D pose of the target, which is then used to generate control inputs. IBVS instead computes the control error directly in image space, avoiding explicit pose reconstruction but still requiring depth cues.

More recently, the rise of Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) has inspired the development of End-to-End controllers capable of learning robust VAT policies from data. These methods directly couple perception and control showing impressive results in ground robots and constrained scenarios [2], [3]. However, their application to aerial platforms remains limited: existing works often rely on simplifying assumptions, such as discrete action spaces [4] or restricted target types, which compromise robustness and generalization.

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Fig. 1. Methodology Overview.

To overcome these limitations, in this work we investigate two complementary strategies for VAT of MAVs Fig. 1. The first follows a modular design, where perception and control components are trained or tuned separately. The second adopts an End-to-End approach, in which a single policy maps raw visual observations directly into continuous control actions through DRL. By contrasting these two paradigms, we aim to assess their respective strengths and limitations in terms of robustness, generalization, and deployability on lightweight aerial platforms.

II. PROJECT MOTIVATION AND METHODOLOGY

Our research is driven by practical constraints and the goal of bridging the gap between simulation and field-ready VAT solutions for lightweight aerial platforms. MAVs face tight payload, compute, and energy limits, which pushes us toward compact, latency-aware perception and control pipelines. By prioritizing lightweight and integrated solutions, we aim to enable VAT in realistic outdoor missions such as infrastructure monitoring, environmental exploration, or search-and-rescue, where external localization may be unavailable.

Purely model-based controllers such as PID or LQR remain attractive for their predictability and certified stability margins [1], but they struggle in scenarios with strong nonlinearities, occlusions, or unmodeled dynamics. Conversely, DRL-based controllers can extract richer visual features and adapt to disturbances but often lack theoretical guarantees [2], [3]. Instead of committing to a single design, our work systematically benchmarks two complementary strategies. On one hand, modular pipelines couple specialized perception networks with classical controllers, offering interpretability and established stability properties. On the other hand, end-to-end learning approaches integrate perception and control into a single trainable policy, with the potential to extract richer features and adapt to complex disturbances.

In our setting, both the tracker and the target are free-flying MAVs operating in full 3D. The tracker uses only the incoming stream of rectified stereo frames to drive the

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS IN THE BOX ENVIRONMENTS AND IN THE PHOTOREALISTIC SCENARIOS (URBAN, PARK AND OFFICE)

Method	Experimental Scenarios and Metrics															
	Box Environments				Urban				Park				Office			
	P_θ	P_ϕ	P_ρ	P_c	P_θ	P_ϕ	P_ρ	P_c	P_θ	P_ϕ	P_ρ	P_c	P_θ	P_ϕ	P_ρ	P_c
Modular LQR	0.27	0.20	0.20	0.22	0.10	0.08	0.07	0.09	0.37	0.27	0.27	0.30	0.11	0.08	0.09	0.09
Modular PID	0.65	0.65	0.55	0.62	0.57	0.56	0.46	0.53	0.94	0.93	0.76	0.88	0.78	0.75	0.67	0.73
End-to-End DRL	0.94	0.94	0.86	0.91	0.94	0.94	0.91	0.93	0.95	0.95	0.92	0.94	0.95	0.95	0.86	0.92

control loop and generate continuous commands that satisfy the tracking objective.

In the modular setting, perception and control are treated as distinct blocks. At the perception layer, state-of-the-art vision networks are employed: a YOLOv12 detector [5] provides robust target acquisition under challenging illumination or scale variations, while a SiamRPN++ tracker [6] maintains a stable target lock at high frame rates. These components are complemented by stereo depth cues, which provide reliable metric distance estimates and allow the recovery of relative 3D target pose with respect to the tracker. The resulting perception outputs feed into different control policies. Three families of controllers are considered, *i.e.*, PID, LQR, and DRL controller. This modular pipeline is designed to emphasize clarity of function separation, making it possible to benchmark how well different control strategies exploit the same vision-based input.

The second methodological direction is a fully End-to-End VAT policy, in which perception and control are learned jointly within a single deep network. Here, the agent directly receives rectified stereo image sequences and produces continuous thrust and angular-rate commands. We adopt an asymmetric actor-critic scheme [3]. End-to-End learning is expected to exploit richer visual cues and capture nonlinear interactions that modular designs might miss. At the same time, it introduces challenges in training stability, sim-to-real transfer, and interpretability.

III. EXPERIMENTS

Our approach is evaluated on two environment types: Box Environments, which resemble the training scenes but with different room shapes, object layouts, and textures; and more complex, photo-realistic environments (Urban, Park, and Office), designed to test D-VAT’s generalization capabilities.

To evaluate VAT performance, we adapted standard tracking metrics to a 3D setting, expressing the target’s position relative to the tracker in spherical coordinates (ρ, θ, ϕ) aligned with the tracker’s body frame. The metrics include: **Distance Score** (ability to maintain the desired distance ρ^*), **Elevation Score** (vertical alignment of the target with the center of the FoV, θ^*), and **Azimuth Score** (horizontal alignment with the center of the FoV, ϕ^*). A **Total Score** is computed as the average of these three metrics, reaching 1 for perfect tracking:

$$\tilde{P}_c(k) = \frac{\tilde{P}_\rho(k) + \tilde{P}_\theta(k) + \tilde{P}_\phi(k)}{3}.$$

Scores are then averaged over the episode time and across 20 runs per scenario to provide a robust performance measure:

$$P_m = \frac{1}{20N_e} \sum_{i=1}^{20} \sum_{k=0}^{N_c-1} \tilde{P}_m^{(i)}(k), \quad m \in \{\rho, \theta, \phi, c\},$$

where N_c is the number of samples per episode and $\tilde{P}_m^{(i)}(k)$ indicates the performance of the i -th run.

Preliminary results are summarized in Table I. All investigated approaches are capable of accomplishing the VAT task. End-to-End DRL pipelines generally achieve higher performance in simulation. However, their effectiveness drops in real-world conditions due to the difficulty of achieving zero-shot sim-to-real transfer. In contrast, modular policies exhibit better transfer from simulation to reality, despite lower performance in simulation. These findings suggest two complementary directions for future work: improving the robustness of End-to-End approaches to reduce the sim-to-real gap, and enhancing the performance of modular pipelines to better leverage their reliable real-world transfer.

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